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PSEUDO HAPTIC IN AUGMENTED REALITY ENVIRONMENT BASED ON TOUCH SCREEN.

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In Augment Reality (AR) environment, human perception could help virtual object mixing with real environment to intensify its reality. Human's sensory sometimes make a cross effect on each other, by controlling visual effects and interactive feedback on touch-screen, we could take advantage of cross-sensory interaction to create a tactile illusion called pseudo-haptic. This investigation would focus on this field, describe the theory and experiment plan of making virtual perception in AR-environment with touch screen interface; implement pseudo-haptic AR system on a Tablet PC, without additional device, generate a sense of touch by pushing and pressing operation, probing into physical property of augmented objects.

Keywords: Augmented reality, touch screen, pseudo-haptic

INTRODUCTION

Augmented Reality (AR) enables virtual objects to be augmented into the physical plane, generated by real-time rendering and position locating, allowing users to interact with both the virtual and real environment. With improvements in hardware efficiency, AR has gained popularity since its use in the multimedia field nowadays.

The main idea of AR is to add artificial objects on in the real world, making the virtual and the reality coexisted in the same space. Hence, in order to increase as possible realism, it is necessary to accomplish as much similarity with the real world and humans receive outside information from their sensory receptors (e.g., eyes, ears) the raw message becomes a sense or concept after some complex

processing in the brain. Perception is how people feel and how they realize the things happened. In contrast to the long history of research in virtual environmental perception, there is little discussion in AR field (Wagner, Broll et al. 2009), most of the research highlights the motion or tactile simulation and focuses on reproducing environmental factors through on external machine. However, due to the limitation of hardware ability achieving human cognitive features in an artificial environment is a popular topic in the realm of Virtual Reality (VR). In addition to reconstructing the whole environment, another way to produce a well-perceived experience at present is to utilize the principle of cross-modal interaction; to accomplish full perception with fragmented information, complete the missing part using another sense (Le´cuyer 2009).

A human's five sense sometimes interacts with each other and may result in cross effects, by controlling visual effects and interactive feedback on a touch-screen, we can take advantage of cross-sensory effects to create an illusion of touch called pseudo-haptic (Biocca, Kim et al. 2001; Le´cuyer 2009), making user "feeling" they are really control or interact with the augmented object in the screen.

Most of the AR research focuses on head-mount display (HMD) issues, but little attention has been paid to touch screen interface (Regenbrecht and Schubert 2002). This investigation would put emphasis on this new field, making virtual perception in AR-environment with touch screen interface. A pseudo-haptic AR system on a Tablet PC would be implemented. Without any additional device, generating a sense of touch by pushing and

pressing, probing into the mass and elasticity of augmented objects, applying physical properties on virtual objects with efficiency, satisfying human perception with restricted resources, enrich the depth of user experience.

RELATED WORK

AUGMENTED REALITY

Augmented Reality (AR) is defined as the technology that combines real and computer-generated information in a real environment, aligns virtual objects interactively with physical ones in real time (Milgram, Takemura et al. 1994). AR is also a subfield of the broader concept of mixed reality (MR); compared with VR, AR augmented virtual objects or scenes on the real environment, making it closer to the real world side in Milgram's Reality-Virtuality Continuum. Owing to the limitation of see-through display, the form of video-base AR environment is the mainstream nowadays. By receiving video from front-side camera, the augmented content could be overlaid on its output screen by camera calibration techniques.

AR technology enables a real space been mutated into a semi-virtual space by providing the mixed sensations of real and virtual objects to a user. Current visual AR applications has come to maturity and been applied to stimulation tools such as surgical training, industrial manufacturing and entertainment field (Azuma 1997).

CROSS-SENSORY

Different Sensory takes in different form of information; it suggests that human's perception is multimodal, which means human could receive information from more than one sensory modality. Sometimes two or more of sensory might link with each other and been corresponded in brain, it is so-called cross-modal effect. McGurk Effect is one of a well-known example of this effect, a perceptual phenomenon that an interaction occurred between hearing and vision in speech perception, seeing by ears and hearing by eyes

In the occasion of cross-modal effect, the perception of a sensation is altered due to other stimuli that are

received through the other senses in the meantime. However, individual would make up a deficiency sense by another sensory in some cases, come up an integrated perception by incomplete factor (Figure 1). Perceptual illusions is one kind of intermodal integration in the form of cross-modal interactions, which means individual uses sensory cues in one modality to complete the missing parts of perceptual experience (Biocca, Kim et al. 2001).

Figure 1. Path analysis indicating a relationship between presence and cross-modal illusions (redraw from Biocca, et al., 2001).

In the field of perception in virtual environment, there are several studies on creating perceptual illusions such as size-weight illusion, elasticity, texture, and friction (Biocca, Kim et al. 2001). Nusseck utilized computer simulation tool to simulate a scene of bouncing ball on horizontal plane to study the correspondence between human's ability of estimating the elasticity and future path of virtual balls (Nusseck, Lagarde et al. 2007). Their three experiments discuss about the human perception of the ball's elasticity, how participants interacted with the ball and the participants' prediction of its trajectory. The results suggest that passive perception against predicting actively future behavior is based on different strategies and information sources. The content about control variables and design of experiments could be a proper referral for this research.

In Narumi's study, researchers apply the complexity of the gustatory system and conduct a pseudo-gustatory display which represents flavors by its visual feedback that enables participant to experience various tastes without changing their chemical composition (Narumi, Sato et al. 2010). Their experiment is performed to evaluate the influence of cross-sensory effects by laying virtual color over actual drinks and recording the responses

of participant. The result shows that even people's experience fundamental tastes could not be changed, that visual feedback sufficiently affects the perception of flavor.

PSEUDO-HAPTIC

Beside the stimulation of visual and audio environment, modulation of tactile or texture are also important issues in virtual reality. Former research usually utilize 3D force/torque sensor to conduct the texture or displacement-force relation, there are much type of haptic display such as force-feedback interface, tactile display and thermal display (Jeon and Choi 2009). The common point of this kind of equipment is the ability of supplying the sense of stiffness or friction by motor or pump. There are various sizes and standards of haptic display for different purpose, most of models are constructed by machinery or physical strength, users would receive haptic feedback by holding the attached ball on robotic arm, according specific algorism to produce the vectors and the value of generated force.

Pseudo-haptic feedback is a technique for simulating haptic sensations; it meant to create haptic sensations in virtual environments using visual feedback and the properties of human visuo-haptic perception (Le´cuyer 2009). For example, asking user to manipulates an object in the virtual environment and makes the target object moving a little bit slower on a specific point to gives the user an impression of resistance and friction. Pseudo-haptic feedback uses visual information to distort human perception and approach sensory illusion. It has been used to simulate various haptic properties such as the stiffness of a virtual spring, the texture of an image or the mass of a virtual object.

According to Le´cuyer's research, there are three outstanding points between traditional haptic feedback systems and pseudo-haptic feedback(Le´cuyer 2009):

- Pseudo-haptic feedback does not necessarily require a haptic interface like traditional way.
- Pseudo-haptic feedback does not using tangible devices or props which has the same constant

shape as the object being manipulated in the virtual environment.

- Pseudo-haptic combines visual feedback and visuo-haptic interactions to simulate a sensation on the haptic channel.

In Biocca's experiment, participants are demand to manipulate the visual analog of a physical force in the experimental virtual environment (Biocca, Kim et al. 2001); a virtual spring which allocated a haptic sensations of physical resistance are effective to participants even though the interface included no haptic displays. A path model of the data reveals that this cross-modal illusion is correlated with and consists of the sensation of spatial and sensory presence, it shows that the integration of multimodal perceptual cues can be applied to produce a consistent experience of a virtual object or spaces from an impoverished, incomplete, and often inconsistent association of sensory cues, generating the illusion of presence in virtual environments.

Pseudo-haptic feedback generates an analogous sense of touch without external space and expensive equipment. This technic could be benefit to touch-screen AR environment, valuable on mobile or domestic appliances. However, due to the dependence on the combination of user's sensorimotor actions in the simulation, the diversity of potency and user experience would be an uncertain factor to the application. Therefore Pseudo-haptic system should avoid with specific occasions such as industrial or scientific apparatus, which depend on precise positioning and feedback from physical Interface.

THEORY

When an individual controls a virtual object on the touch screen, the target object will not react in real-time, but will, instead present an adjusted deviation between normal situations. The unexpected visual feedback causes a sense of unbalance between our perception and our expectation; this leads to a corrected instruction from brain which makes body follow the adjusted speed unconsciously. At the same time, the tactile information on the skin also changes because of the revised movement and perception and sensation synchronize with each

other gradually. When both of them reach equilibrium, the brain accepts a concept of their realism and an illusion of virtual physics property is constituted successfully (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Pseudo-haptic AR system on touch screen.

Following steps are the composing procedure of pseudo-haptic on touch screen AR environment:

- The user controls the virtual object with their body in an AR environment.
- The target object makes a move based on its appropriated setting.
- The motion feedback of the object is received through the human-vision-system.
- The visual message of the feedback is transported to the user’s brain which identified the inaccuracy between their expectation and perception.
- In order to correct the error in perception, the limbs are commanded to correct their motion.
- The body modulate the controlling motion after receive the order of correction,.
- Due to the amending decision, the tactile message is changed with the altered movement.

This cycle repeats very quickly, and then user’s brain and limbs adjust and integrated the difference between them until they reach a harmonic state.

The human brain tend to comprehend uncompleted perception by using a template given in their mental representations .The main purpose of this research is

to utilize cross-modal sensory perception to replenish the sense of haptic, by assuming the perception of physics and increasing the believability of the virtual object. Cross-modal interaction can provide visual and tactile feedback in interaction process; construct an immersive AR environment.

COGNITIVE MODULE

Perception is the process through which an organism attains awareness or understanding of its environment by organizing and interpreting sensory information. If we define respectively, the brain as a machine and liken stimuli and reactions to raw materials and end items, we input a sensation message at the beginning and obtain the result of perception at the end. The processing step can be regarded as a checkpoint in a product line with each stage consisting of particular purpose.

The following figure lists the dissolution of the physics perception procedure (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Cognitive module of pseudo-haptic AR.

- Message Level: it represents the raw data (e.g., visual, auditory) which received by human sensory.
- Stimuli Level: stimuli are energy patterns which are registered by the senses. After distilling the raw message, the basic elements of sensation are given (e.g., color or physical property of an object).
- Variable Level: The formation of a specific perception (e.g., appearance or the features of an object).

In this research, the control variable is the stimuli in the second level; by adjusting the color or physical property of a virtual object, we can observe the change in the accuracy of physical perception.

EXPERIMENT

This study probe into the interaction between user and touch-screen AR device, focused on the variation after user get the target. The experiment inspired by Nusseck's path prediction test (Nusseck, et al., 2007), carrying out two sections; each experimental environment is constrained to a simple object interaction. The control group only contains passive visual clue, the experimental group includes interactive feedback.

Figure 4 (Left)-control group. (Right)- experimental group

Our experiment was taken one on one within doors; participant and recorder sit in front of the desk, holding the tablet pc with a web camera attached. The experimental platform is the open-source AR environment developing tool FLARToolkit, the motion of dynamic scene was calculated through a series of tween equation. In order to formulate the appropriate parameters for the virtual object, a pilot test was carried out to examine the correlation of the trajectory with a real world situation.

There are total 15 samples in a round, which is sorted by the volume of augmented object: big, middle and small. Every sample in each union would be set up one kind of physical property into 5 levels (e.g. 1: least elastic, 5: most elastic); only one of the physical properties would be arranged in the meantime.

Participants were the graduate students from the Institute of Industrial Design of National Chen Kung University age between 20 and 30; there are 30 validation samples, including 12 male and 18 female. After watching the demo, participant are asking to look at an dynamic virtual ball augmented in the real

world on touch screen AR environment and report the allocated score of target ball by 5 point Likert scale.

This study is trying to compare the reported value from perceiving the virtual object and the actual parameter, validates participant's physical perception by their rating accuracy.

CONTROL GROUP

In this section, control variables were the physical property of the target object; evaluation indicators were the accuracy of each sample. There are three rounds in this section (Figure 5): the first round is observing the virtual ball free falls and bounces, control variables are the elasticity of the sample ball. The second round is letting the sample cube been hit by another virtual cube and move; control variable is the density of the target. In the third round sample cube is pushing by an invisible force and slide through the desk; control variable is the friction of the cube.

Figure 5. Three rounds in control group. (A) elasticity (B) density (C) friction.

EXPERIMENTAL GROUP

Continued from the preceding experiment, samples in experimental group include interactive feedback. Participant needs to perform an active task such as pushing or moving an augmented virtual cube to interact with another augmented virtual object, predicts property of the moving object. The validity of this section would be compared with former result.

There are also three rounds in this section (Figure 6). The first round is asking participant to drag and release the sample object, control variables are the same with the first part. In the second round participant will manipulate a virtual cube to hit the other cube and estimate how target moves, control variable is still the density of the ball. The mission of participants in third round is grabbing a cube to slide on the ground; control variable is also associated with the former section.

Figure 6. Three rounds in passive visual clue only. (A) elasticity (B) density (C) friction.

RESULT

The results of experiments would be separated into three values to discuss the (i) liner regressions, the (ii) accuracy of allocated score sorting by physical properties and (iii) volume of samples in both groups.

LINER REGRESSION

The graph of (Figure 7) shows the values of the slopes for the linear regressions and the R^2 for each condition. The slope of liner regression represents the specific value between participants' intuition and actual answer. Compare to the slope value of control group, the same parameter in experiment group are closer to 1. All specific values in both groups are bigger than 1, that means the actual value is generally bigger than the estimated one, and the trend of prediction in experiment group is more similar to the exact value.

As for the R^2 value of liner regression, the correlation coefficients for these conditions are quite high in both elasticity and friction rounds. The R square in experimental group condition is higher than the other of control group which reveals that by adding passive visual clue, the sample in experiment group shows a better correlation with the correct number.

Figure 7 (UP) Slope values calculated through a linear regression for each condition. (Down) R square for each condition. The fourth condition is the group average.

PHYSICAL PROPERTY

In this experiment, the mean of deviation of participant’s answer and actual value stands for the accuracy of each sample. The line chart of deviation of all 15 samples sketch a rough trend of 3 wave; the middle level such like 2,3 and 4 have higher deviation than level 1 and 5(Figure 8). It is obvious that physical property level of samples could affect their rate of been judged correctly; the higher deviation means those situations are harder to be predicted closely with correct ones.

In control group, the deviation of three rounds in line chart is similar; but the trend changed massively in experimental group, the performance of participants improves in elasticity and friction round instead the deviation of density round raised. It shows the addition of dynamic clue and interactive feedback can possibly revise the performance of participants in appraising bounce and slide motion, making their prediction closer to the exact value in experiment environment.

Figure 8 (Up) Mean deviation of allocated score in control group. (Down) Mean deviation of allocated score in experimental group.

VOLUME

Over all, sample unite of middle volume has the highest accuracy of prediction; on the other hand, samples of big and small volume are easier been valued with bias (Figure 9). In experimental group,

participants recognizes elasticity and friction more efficiency in all condition, however the addition of interactive feedback causes clear deviations in density round except big volume sample unite.

Figure 9 Mean deviation which sorting by the sample volume in (Up) Control group. (Down) Experimental group.

CONCLUSION

Together, These findings suggest that the value of R² and the slope of the regression in experimental group represent better than control group, participant’s allocated score is in direct ratio to the actual parameter, but the accuracy of reported value is not quite high since human’s perception of static and dynamic scenes is not very sensitive(O’Sullivan 2005).

While the mean of deviation of control group is 0.914, the experiment group has the lower mean as 0.878. The analysis has been done with a 2-tailed dependent measures t-test (α=95%); the possibility of t-test is 0.605 and reach a statistical level of significance. This result concludes that the combining of visual clue with operating gesture in this experiment decrease the value of deviation effectively, makes the dynamic scene cognitively easy to predict and correct the interference of sample’s volume.

DISCUSSION

Since interacting with virtual object in the AR environment is a human-computer-interaction issue; there could have several possible evaluation in the future work: (i) the correlation coefficients of accuracy and consuming time in a single task, the subjective scale for participant's (ii) workload and (iii) preferences for the new design in this study.

Compare to the traditional video-based AR system on touch screen, the Pseudo-haptic AR system represent better performance and higher fascination. This design has plenty of potential to be practical use. This work could be taken into account in AR interface design in touch-screen environment. Based on the method of pseudo-tactile, increasing physical fidelity on AR platform without extra space; helping designer accomplishes better quality in most efficient way, provide a cognitive-base method to optimize the sense of reality. Being helpful on operating video game or virtual interface, enhance the effect of motion sensing and the depths of presence.

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